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STRATEGIC HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES AND ITS IMPACT ON WORK LIFE BALANCE OF EMPLOYEES OF AUTOMOBILE INDUSTRY IN PUNE REGION

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Abstract

Various strategic practices have already been established to promote the value of Human Resource Management in organizations. The Human Resource Management function is now considered as a strategic tool in the formulation and implementation of organizational strategies to attain its objectives. Automobile Industries are chosen as subjects for this study with specific aspects relating to various strategic human resource management practices and its impact on work-life balance and to determine its prevalence on the mentioned industry is the main objective of this study.

Organizations focus upon increased revenue generated by its employees, competitive workforce and employee dedication for achieving its strategic goals in order to meet the challenges of 21st century. The current research builds upon the considerable knowledge related to the theory and practices of work-life balance. It helps the organization to improve productivity, efficiency, competitiveness, morale and hence gain a competitive edge. Similarly employees are benefited from work-life balance initiatives through increased motivation to work, enhanced satisfaction, empowerment and ultimately more commitment to the organization.

The study will be focus on main objectives, to study impacts of human resource management strategic practices on work-life balance and develop policies and to study the relationship between each of the Individual related variables, Family related variables, Work related variables and Work-life balance of Automobile Industries. Also to study the work-family conflicts levels, Job satisfaction of employees and to study the various work-life balance problems faced by them while working in the Industry and remedial measure to achieve better work-life balance of the employees in the Automobile Industry.

Work-life Balance is a broad concept including proper prioritizing between "work" on one hand and "life" on the other. This in turns leads to real benefits for the employer in terms of productivity gains, lowered turnover rate, a stronger team spirit, and loyalty to the employer.

Key Areas: SHRM practices, Work-life balance, Individual, Family, & Work related variables for balancing the work, Work-Life Conflict, & Job satisfaction

1. Introduction

Human Resource Management function is now considered as a strategic tool in the formulation and implementation of organizational strategies to attain its objectives. The function of work before which was a matter of necessity and survival has evolved encouraging organizations to create and establish new standards that will

encourage employee retention and personal satisfaction. Automobile Industries are chosen as subjects for this study with specific aspects relating to work-life balance and various strategic human resource management practices to determine its prevalence on the mentioned industry is the main objective of this study.

Organizations focus upon increased revenue generated by its employees, competitive workforce and employee dedication for achieving its strategic goals in order to meet the challenges of 21st century. However, in this era of hyper competition work life balance of employees' at all managerial levels has been affected enormously. This exploratory study deliberates upon a brief elaboration of work-life balance, its importance for the organizations and the various emerging practices/initiatives associated with it.

The current research builds upon the considerable knowledge related to the theory and practices of work-life balance. The findings reveal that work-life balance is both important for the organization and for its employee's particularly in current dynamic organizational scenarios. It helps the organization to improve productivity, efficiency, competitiveness, morale and hence gain a competitive edge. Similarly employees are benefited from work-life balance initiatives through increased motivation to work, enhanced satisfaction, empowerment and ultimately more commitment to the organization.

Work-life balance has become a challenge for the organizations because of an increased need to improve the morale of the employees, maintaining and retaining them with a precious knowledge of the Industry and keeping up the speed with the current trends in the workplace.

This study elaborates work-life balance, how it can be a milestone in workplace harmony and an exploration of various practices that aid in workplace balance.

2. Strategic Human Resource Management Practices

Over the past decade, HR researchers and practitioners have focused their attention on other important questions. First, what determines whether an organization adopts a strategic approach to HRM, and how is HR strategy formulated? Of interest is which organizations are most likely to adopt a strategic approach to HRM. Is there, for example, a positive association with a given set of external and internal characteristics or contingencies and the adoption of SHRM? Another area of interest concerns the policies and practices making up different HR strategies. Does HR strategy really matter? For organizational practitioners who are looking for ways to gain a competitive advantage, the implication of HR strategic choices for company performance is certainly the key factor. Definitions of the Strategic Human Resource Management Practices are:

Hall (1984): "The identification of needed skills and active management of learning for the long range future in relation to explicit corporate and business strategy."

Walton (1999): "Strategic human resource development involves introducing, eliminating, modifying, directing and guiding processes in such a way that all individuals and teams are equipped with the skills, knowledge and competences they require to undertake current and future tasks required by the organization."

3. Work Life Balance

What is work life balance?

Work is physical or mental efforts put by us to do/produce or accomplish something. It is generally referred as a job or activity that you do regularly especially in order to earn money.

Life refers to one's personal lives, experiences and responsibilities outside and beyond the work place. For many these include families and often the debate of work life balance is referred to as work family balance.

Work –life balance is a concept including proper prioritizing between work (career and ambition) and “lifestyle” (health, pleasure, leisure, family and spiritual development/meditation).

Work life balance is used to describe the equilibrium between responsibilities at work and responsibilities outside paid work; having a work life balance means that this equilibrium is in the right position for the individual concerned. For some people it means spending more time in paid work and less time at home, while for others it means ensuring that paid work does not infringe on time needed for other responsibilities. It is about managing our work commitments with career goals, and our responsibilities at home and the wider community.

Work life and personal life are inter-connected and interdependent. Now many organizations come up with new schemes, procedures and policies to deal with work life imbalance problem.

Work-life balance is about helping staff to maintain healthy, rewarding lifestyles that will in turn lead to improvements in productivity and performance. Strategies to achieve balance will differ between organisations, partly depending on their function, the types of work roles they offer, and their workforce profile. Definitions of the work-life balances are:

Clark (2000) defined that “Satisfaction and good functioning at work and at home with a minimum of role conflict”.

Deery (2008) defined the concept of WLB is a complex task, as it can be viewed from the meaning of ‘work’, ‘life’ and ‘balance’.

Emslie and Hunt (2009) argued that “work-life balance defined as ‘satisfaction and good functioning at work and at home, with a minimum of role conflict’.

4. Impacts of Strategic HRM Practices on Work Life Balance

The implementation of strategic HRM is carried out within the framework of the approaches of a systematic review and set out within a clear framework. It must be emphasized that HR strategies are not just ad hoc programmes, policies, or plans concerning HR issues that the HR department happens to feel are important.

4.1 Human Resource Planning-Human resource planning is based on the belief that people are an organization's most important strategic resource.

4.2 Recruitment and Selection-Recruitment and selection also have an important role to play in ensuring worker performance and positive organisational outcomes.

4.3 Induction-Induction is the process of receiving and welcoming employees when they first join a company and giving them the basic information they need to settle down quickly and happily and start work.

4.4 Training & Development-Training is the use of systematic and planned instruction activities to promote learning. It involves the use of formal processes to impart knowledge and help people to acquire the skills necessary for them to perform their jobs satisfactorily.

4.5 Performance Appraisal-Performance appraisal is a systematic way of reviewing and assessing the performance of an employee during a given period of time and planning for his future.

4.6 Compensation-The elements in the compensation package include perks which are elements like free use of facilities, club membership, cheap loans, housing etc. Benefits are pension, medical insurance, holidays and accidents, disability and death insurance.

4.7 Employee Relations-Employee relations strategies define the intentions of the organization about what needs to be done and what needs to be changed in the ways in which the organization manages its relationships with employees and their trade unions.

4.8 Reward & Award-Reward strategy is a declaration of intent that defines what the organization wants to do in the longer term to develop and implement reward policies, practices and processes that will further the achievement of its business goals and meet the needs of its stakeholders.

4.9 Incentives-Financial incentives are designed to provide direct motivation. A shop floor payment-by-result scheme and a sales representative's commission system are examples of financial incentives.

4.10 Promotion-A promotion policy could state the organization's intention to promote from within wherever this is appropriate as a means of satisfying its requirements for high quality staff.

4.11 Transfer-Transfer policies should establish the circumstances when employees can be transferred and the arrangements for pay, resettlement and retraining.

4.12 Health, Safety, & Environment (HSE)-Health and safety policies and programmes are concerned with protecting employees and other people affected by what the company produces. Safety programmes deal with the prevention of accidents and with minimizing the resulting loss and damage to persons and property.

4.13 Welfare Services-Labour Welfare is a part of social welfare, conceptually & operationally. It covers a broad field & connotes a state of well-being, happiness, satisfaction, conservation & development of human resources.

4.14 Work-Life Balance Policy-Work-life balance policies define how the organization intends to allow employees greater flexibility in their working patterns so that they can balance what they do at work with the responsibilities and interests they have outside work.

4.15 Work Centrality-Work centrality measure with five major domains (work, leisure, community, religion, and family) in their lives, based on their relative centrality.

4.16 Emotional Intelligence-The capacity for recognizing our own feelings and that of others, for motivating ourselves, for managing emotions well in ourselves as well as others.

4.17 Work Flexibility-The work flexibility are Part-time working, Job-sharing, Time-off-in lieu (TOIL), Flexitime, Home working or teleworking, Career breaks, Shift working, Shift swapping, Self-rostering, Annualized hours, Compressed hours, Staggered hours, Additional leave entitlement, Unique working pattern.

5. Importance of Work Life Balance in Today's Scenario

From the perspective of employees, WLB is the maintenance of a balance between responsibilities at work and at home. Work life initiatives are those strategies, policies, programs and practices initiated and maintained in

workplaces to address flexibility, quality of work life and work family conflict. In other words, WLB is about people having a measure of control over when, where and how they work. Strategies of WLB in organizations include policies covering flexible work arrangements, child and dependent care and family and parental leave.

Hence, it would be interesting to study organizational perspectives on work-life balance. Work-life balance is about creating and maintaining supportive and healthy work environments, which will enable employees to have balance between work and personal responsibilities and thus strengthen employee loyalty and productivity.

Today's workers have many competing responsibilities such as work, children, housework, volunteering, spouse and elderly parent care and this places stress on individuals, families and the communities in which they reside.

Work-life conflict is a serious problem that impacts workers, their employers and communities. It seems that this problem is increasing over time due to high female labour force participation rates, increasing numbers of single parent families, the predominance of the dual-earner family and emerging trends such as elder care. It is further exasperated with globalization, an aging population, and historically low unemployment.

6. Different Variables for Balancing the Work

In this study the following variables (individual related, family related and work related) are identified and studied as dependent variables for Work-life balance in Automobile Industry.

6.1 Individual related Variables and Work Life Balance

Individual related variables like gender, age, marital status, emotional intelligence, and work centrality are studied along with work-life balance by various researchers viz. Masood and Mahlawat (2012), Thriveni et al. (2012), Namayandeh and yacoob (2010), Sjoberg (2008) (Emotional Intelligence), Hyman et al (2003) (Work Centrality) and Parasuraman and simmers (2001) were taken into consideration to identify their association with WLB among ITES working professionals.

The following Individual related variables are studied with work life balance-

- a) Age, Gender, Marital Status, Child, and Work Life Balance
- b) Level, Shift, and Health care and Work Life Balance
- c) Work Centrality and Work Life Balance
- d) Emotional Intelligence and Work Life Balance

6.2 Family related Variables and Work Life Balance

Various researchers have considerably investigated the impact of Family related variables and work-life balance. Lee and Waite (2005), Renge (2007) (Household responsibility), Saviour (2009), Sackey (2011) (Spouse support), Jang (2008), Nasurdin and O'Driscoll (2012) (Parental demand). Organisational researchers have linked work-life balance with household responsibility, spouse support, parental demand.

In this investigation household responsibility, spouse support and parental demand have been studied in association with work-life balance.

The following Family related variables are studied with work life balance-

- a) Household responsibility and work- life balance
- b) Spouse support and work- life balance
- c) Parental demands and work- life balance

6.3 Work related Variables and Work Life Balance

Work related variable was also studied along with work-life balance by Hill et al. (2001) (Work schedule flexibility). In the present study work-life balance is studied along with work related variables namely, work load and work schedule flexibility.

Flexible work schedules are those that vary from the standard work schedules of an organization. Since flexible schedules must meet the needs of both the employer and the employee, flexible work schedules are based on worker needs within set parameters approved by a supervisor.

The following Work related variables are studied with work life balance-

- a) Work load and work life balance
- b) Work flexibility and work life balance

7. SHRM Practices/Work Life Balance and Work Family Conflict

The difficulty and forces of work and family may provide increase to work-life balance problems to an human being and as women in workforce have improved significantly, they so face a lot of problems and challenges. They are unmoving observed as the main porters of the home and family, even if they work just as much as men.

Some of their findings explained that single women without children absolutely influence work-life conflict. The interviews presented verification that women's views depend on their marital position. There are also of shift workers who work lastingly at night. It is obvious that the different shift systems in process might have a very different impact on the workers' health and well-being (Boisard, etal, 2002).

In this research a decrease in working hours shows to lower work–life conflict for both men and women. Part time work is also connected with concentrated work pressure but it does so extensively only for women.

8. SHRM Practices/Work Life Balance and Job Satisfaction

The term 'job satisfaction' refers to the attitudes and feelings people have about their work. Positive and favourable attitudes towards the job indicate job satisfaction. Negative and unfavourable attitudes towards the job indicate job dissatisfaction. Morale is often defined as being equivalent to job satisfaction. Thus Guion (1958) defines morale as 'the extent to which an individual's needs are satisfied and the extent to which the individual perceives that satisfaction as stemming from his total work situation'.

Outcome variable also studied along with work-life balance by Gupta and Murthy (1984), and Daga and Husain (1997), Ervin (2012), Adams et al. (1996), Chitra devi and Sheela rani (2012), Karen et al. (2007), Kasimatis and Guastello (2012) found that work life balance affects life satisfaction, job satisfaction, family satisfaction, career satisfaction and job stress.

9. Automobile Industry in India

Today the Indian automobile industry is fulfilling the demand of the Indian as well as consumers in other countries. The Automobile industry is showing is not only meeting the growing demands of the Indian market but also making its presence in the international market rapidly.

Demographically and economically, India's automotive industry is well-positioned for growth, servicing both domestic demand and, increasingly, export opportunities. A predicted increase in India's working-age population is likely to help stimulate the burgeoning market for private vehicles. Rising prosperity, easier access to finance and increasing affordability is expected to see four-wheelers gaining volumes, although two wheelers will remain the primary choice for the majority of purchasers, buoyed by greater appetite from rural areas, the youth market and women.

This exciting outlook for the industry is set against a backdrop of two potentially game-changing transportation trends the gradual legislative move towards greener, gas-based public transport, vehicles and a greater requirement for urban mass mobility schemes to service rapidly-expanding cities.

10. Make in India – Automobiles

The automobile sector of India is one of the largest in the world and accounts for over 7.1 % of India’s gross domestic product (GDP). It also contributes to nearly 22% of the country’s manufacturing GDP. The sector was first opened to foreign direct investment (FDI) in the year 1991 during the liberalisation of the Indian economy and has come a long way since.

- Seventh largest producer in the world with an average annual production of 23.36 Million vehicles.
- Third largest automotive market by volume, by 2016.
- Four large auto manufacturing hubs across the country.
- 7.1% of the country’s GDP by volume.
- Six Million-plus vehicles to be sold annually, by 2020.

With 'Make in India' initiative's key focus sectors being the automobile, railway and renewable energy, various new opportunities are in ZF India's horizon. According to Managing Director of India Mr. Piyush Munot, this gives “the company the confidence to invest further in the country and also produce components not only in India but also the rest of the world”. The Indian government’s focus on improving the infrastructure of the country will also undoubtedly prove to be a boost for the manufacturing sector. Other initiatives such as Skill India, Smart City and Start-Up India will only supplement such growth.

11. Global Scenario of Indian Automobile Industry

The industry being highly capital intensive, has entry barriers for smaller players. Even the existing global auto majors themselves are realigning their production bases coming closer to the scene of action in Asia - Pacific region, mainly in China, India and Thailand. Besides the above, the constant pressure for cost reduction on OEMs is compelling them to outsource more and more components from low cost countries.

The changing scenario has opened up opportunities for Indian automobile industry. India, with huge domestic market, rapidly growing purchasing power, and market linked exchange rate and well established financial market and stable corporate governance framework is emerging as an attractive destination for new investments in this sector.

After liberalization of Indian economy in general and automobile industry in particular, considerable number of Multinational Companies are operating in India either as wholly owned subsidiaries or in collaboration

with their Indian partners. This automotive sector has taken benefit of liberalization of Indian economy to a large extent and made available various international brands in India for Indian consumers. Firms like Hyundai are supplying manufactures cars in the international market using its manufacturing facility in India in a big way. These firms are using locally available efficient and cost competitive huge pool of human resource in India.

12. Automobile Industry in Pune

Pune has the seventh largest metropolitan economy and the sixth highest per capita income in the country. Pune is India's fifth auto motor producing district in India. The automobile sector is prominent in Pune. The establishment of the Maharashtra Industrial Development Corporation (MIDC) by the Government of Maharashtra , the Government five year plans and policies , introduction of the New industrial Policy, 100% foreign direct investment, easy availability of raw material , availability of skilled and unskilled labours are the major factors responsible for the growth and development of the automobile industries in Pune.

Today, Pune has a diverse industrial population .It is one of India's most important automotive hub. Some well-known Indian as well as foreign automobile companies have established their manufacturing units in Pune district. All types of automobile vehicles are manufactured in these companies such as two wheelers, three wheelers and four wheelers including trucks and tractors thereby contributing to the Indian economy. The Automobile companies like Tata motors, Mahindra and Mahindra, Force Motors, General Motors, Mercedes Benz, Volkswagen and Fiat are having their manufacturing plants in Pune.

13. Statement of the problem

Although impact of SHRM practices may be applied on work life balance in Automobile Industry, and they can only contribute optimally to performance for employee are aligned on its objectives and the way in which it is implemented in the organization. Other related research questions included:

1. What is the demographic profile of employees working in the Automobile Industry?
2. What is the perception of employees on their job satisfaction and WLB?
3. What are the problems faced by the employees in balancing the Work Life?
4. What are the predominant SHRM practices taken by the industry for WLB?
5. Has SHRM practices played a strategic role in the Automobile Industry?
6. How the HRM strategies and WLB adopted by the industry, contributed to job satisfaction and performance?

14. Objectives of the Research

1. To study the demographic profile of the employees of Automobile Industry in Pune region.
2. To understand the perceptions of respondents with respect to Job satisfaction and Work-Life Balance.
3. To study the Work-Family Conflicts levels of employees of Automobile Industry.
4. To study the Work-Life Balance of the employees and the various problems faced by them while working in the Automobile Industry.
5. To study the individual related variables; family related variables; work related variables and Work-Life Balance of Automobile Industry.
6. To study the Strategic Human Resource Management practices and its impact on Work-Life Balance of employees of Automobile Industry.

15. Scopes of the Study

The word 'Automobile' includes all types of motor vehicles. However, the study covers total 11 Industries in Pune Region. This study tries to contribute to the discussion by determining the presence of SHRM practices specifically on work-life balance on Automobile Industry that will enhance industry's performance and to achieve competitive advantage. Automobile Industry involved in this study has shown explicable ways of promoting these efforts and have given a relative importance in treating this subject with biggest concern.

16. Significance of the Study

Most organizations have been thriving of setting up quality standards to its internal workforce by starting to re-invent their SHRM Practices. Such practices varies and this study tries to find out whether such practices are being implemented or applied by Automobile Industries and in order to demonstrate this, the researcher has specifically selected work-life balance and labor relations.

17. Benefits of the Study

17.1. Benefits for the Employee

Many factors improve where the employee is able to find the right balance. Some of these factors, according to Vlems (2005) include:

1. Improved employee's happiness and better relations with management.
2. Employees would be happier when they are able to balance their work and life demands.
3. The advantages of many organizations come from happy employees.
4. Improved relations with management.
5. Perceived support of management towards employees' work-life balance fosters a good relationship between the workforce and management which itself improves effective communication within the Industry.
6. Improved employees' self-esteem, health, concentration, and confidence.
7. Greater responsibility and a sense of ownership.
8. One UK study reports that more than forty percent of employees are neglecting other aspects of their life because of work, which may increase their vulnerability to mental health problems (Mental Health Foundation, 2012).

17.2 Benefits for the Employer

Generally, the following factors, as Vlems (2005) notes, improve for the employer:

1. Employee loyalty and commitment. These increase with opportunities for work-life balance.
2. Employees are more likely to stay with an organisation when there are opportunities for achieving work-life balance.
3. Tasks are managed better, there is increased motivation, and there is reduction in the level of stress among employees.
4. The balance makes employees feel valuable.
5. Implementing work-life balance programmes gives an impression that the organization cares about the employees. Thus, they will feel more valuable and work harder as a result.
6. The work environment will be less stressful; which means, less stress related illnesses and decreased health care costs.

7. The presence of work-life balance programmes in an organization makes it attractive to a wider range of candidates when it comes to recruitment.
8. The workforce will be more loyal and motivated.
9. Business will attract and retain the best people.
10. Increased employee retention, productivity and profit.
11. Reduced absenteeism and maximized available labour.

18. Review of Literature

The review of related literature specified in this study facilitates the purpose to where we can explore or explain the significance of SHRM and work life balance its presence on Pune firms. It would promote further an understanding of the conceptual framework of this study. Similar and related studies were noted to help show that SHRM and WLB is a subject that needs to be undertaken and viewed to be important in order to gain competitive advantage and explain its global importance. It includes the concerns, issues and the role of government regulation. A discussion or overview on the way firms, not just in the Pune but globally as well is provided.

A speech given by Mr. Ratan Tata- Don't just have career or academic goals. Set goals to give you a balanced, successful life. Balanced means ensuring your health, relationships, mental peace are all in good order. There is no point of getting a promotion on the day of your breakup. There is no fun in driving a car if your back hurts. Shopping is not enjoyable if your mind is full of tensions. Don't take life seriously. Life is not meant to be taken seriously, as we are really temporary here.

We are like a prepaid card with limited validity. If we are lucky, we may last another 50 years. And 50 years is just 2,500 weekends. Do we really need to get so worked up? It's OK, Bunk few classes, score low in couple of papers, take leave from work, fall in love, and fight a little with your spouse. It's ok; we are people, not programmed devices! **"Don't be serious, enjoy Life as it comes."**

19. Research Gap

Prior research identified some support towards SHRM practices on work-life balance through some psychological constructs, but additional research is needed to specify degree of role efficacy, degree of emotional intelligence and impact on work-life balance. There is also a need to examine role efficacy and emotional intelligence of Managers. Work-life balance of career managers as related to family dynamics also needs to be explored. Additional research is needed to explore the family resources and experiences in the Indian context that are associated with different types of enrichment.

20. Hypothesis

Tentative solutions in the form of hypotheses were formulated on the basis of strategic human resource management practices & on the basis of individual related, family related,& work related variable, work- life conflicts identified, and its impact on work life balance and job satisfaction. Based on the above objectives suitable and meaningful hypotheses have been formulated for this study. The studies have been tested the following hypotheses.

There is an impact of Strategic Human Resource practices, individual related variables, family related variables, work related variables, Work-Family Conflict levels, & Job Satisfaction on Work-Life balance of Employees of Automobile Industry.

21. Methodology

Methodology involves the systematic procedures by which the researcher starts from the initial identification of the problem to its final conclusions. Research methodology involves such general activities as identifying problems, review of the literature, formulating hypotheses, procedure for testing hypotheses, measurement, data collection analysis of data, interpreting results and drawing conclusions.

21.1 Research Design

The research design constitutes the blue print for the collection, measurement and analysis of data. The impact of SHRM on work-life balance on selected individual, family, work related variables, and outcome variable are studied in detail.

21.2 Sampling Design

In order to obtain objectives, the industries located in Pune are to be selected and analysis has been done on this basis. The responses of Junior level, Middle level, and Senior level employees have been taken from 11 Automobile Industry in Pune Region. In determining the size and nature of the sample, Men and Women working professionals have been selected from Automobile Industry.

The convenience sampling technique has been chosen and it is suitable for selecting the sample from the Automobile Industry working professionals. The 400 respondents have been taken as a sample from 11 Automobile Industry in Pune region.

21.3 Data Sources

The focus of this research is to study the SHRM practices and its impact on WLB of employees in Automobile Industries. Data for the study were collected through the primary sources.

21.3.1 Primary Data

The primary data are collected from the respondents through a questionnaire. The study was conducted with the help of the structured questionnaire, Discussions/Personal interviews, and Observation which was administered among the sample of 400 respondents from 11 Automobile Industry.

21.3.2 Secondary Data

The secondary data are collected from the secondary sources, these sources which record an event or happening that was never actually witnessed by the researcher. The latest information related to the study was gathered from the libraries in Pune. Websites and portals were also used to collect some statistical information for Pune Region. A number of standards textbooks in the area of SHRM, WLB and Research Methodology were also referred to present the theoretical perspective.

21.4 Tools Used for Data Collection

A personal survey has been conducted in different Automobile Industry. The survey has been conducted through a distribution of questionnaire which consists of different sections and questions for the respondent that holds various positions in the Industry.

This scale is named after Renis Likert. This is the most widely used scale in research, in particular, in testing models. Several research studies are done using Likert scale. The respondents require indicating a degree of

agreement of disagreement with each of a series of statements about the stimulus objects. The following table illustrates the rating scheme will be used by the respondents in answering the questionnaire.

Table	
Score(Out of 5)	Implementation
1	Strongly disagree
2	Disagree
3	Neutral
4	Agree
5	Strongly agree

21.5 Statistical Tools used for Analysis

Descriptive statistics (Mean, Median, Mode, standard deviation) will be computed to study the nature of distribution of scores on various variables of the study. The correlations between individual, family, and work related variables, and work life balance and its dimensions have been calculated to ascertain the extent of relationship between these variables.

One way analysis of variance (ANOVA) has been used to study the main effect of individual, family, and work related variables on work life balance and its dimensions. Further, t-test, skewness, kurtosis and regression have been applied to study the differences in work life balance of Automobile Industry with respect to age, gender and marital status.

22. Limitations of the Study

1. This convinced me that Pune city is a good field for research for Automobile Industry as it is a well-developed city industrially speaking and is renowned for its zones at Pune, Pimpri-Chinchwad, Sanaswadi and Ranjangaon and Chakan MIDC. Therefore I decided to limit my research sample for the various strategic human resource management practices and its impact on work life balance of employees of Automobile Industry within the Pune Region.
2. It is very difficult to accurately assess when all information about these dimensions have been derived from the same perspective.
3. A large number of human resource management strategic has been focused on Senior, Middle and Junior levels of employees.
4. The SHRM & Work Life Balance connection is difficult to accurately assess when all information about these dimensions has been derived from the same perspective.
5. It is very difficult to take appointment for collecting primary data from Industry.
6. Some respondents seemed to in a hurry while filling the questionnaire, also they answered randomly making it hard to interpret.
7. Some employees were not willing to disclose their personal or family matters which could not be assessed for want of recorded data and information.
8. As the employees were so busy, it was too difficult for them give some time for the study and some working employees hesitated to give their own opinions.
9. Sample for survey was not enough.

23. Major findings

23.1 Findings Based on Demographic Segmentation

1. From the result table, it is observed that most of the employees (92.0%) in automobile industry are males.
2. From the above table, it is observed that maximum numbers of the employees (52.0%) are in age group of 31-40 years.
3. From the result, it is indicate that most of the employees (38.2%) are from junior level employees in automobile industry.
4. Result also shows that maximum numbers of the employees (73.7%) are working in either general shift or day shift.
5. From the result, it is observed that most of the employees (74.7%) are in this research are married.
6. From the result, it is shown that most of the employees (62.8%) spouses are employed.
7. From the result, it can be observed that the maximum numbers of employee (52.3%) have only one child.
8. It is found that 100 % employees said that there is no disability in their children.
9. It has been found that highest 32.25 of employees having annual income in the range of 3-5 lakhs in automobile industry.

23.2 Findings on overall impacts of Strategic Human Resource Management Practices on Work Life Balance in Selected Automobile Industry

23.2.1 Human Resource Planning

10. From the result, it can be seen that most of the employees (73.0%) are agree for human resource planning system is aligned with business requirement.
11. From the result, it is observed that maximum numbers of the employees (77.8%) are agreeing for organization plan human resources requirement well in advance.
12. From the result, it can be observed that most of the employees (70.0%) agree for organization HR planning system is able to provide manpower as per business needs.
13. From the result, it can be seen that most of the employees (63.0%) are agreeing for ensuring adequate supply of manpower.
14. Results found that 53.5% of the employees are strongly agree for anticipating the impact of technology on jobs and requirements for more human resources.

23.2.2 Recruitment, Selection & Induction

15. From the result, it is indicating that maximum numbers of employees (43.8%) of the employees are strongly agreed for industry having a structured recruitment system and definite budget.
16. From the result, it is found that most of the employees (42.5%) are agree for adequate and relevant information about the organization and job is provided to the candidate at the time of recruitment.
17. From the result, it is seen that maximum number of employees (42.1%) are agree for selection of a candidate in our organization is strictly based on his/her merit.
18. From the result, it is found that most of the employees (70.0%) are agree for our organization places the right person in the right job.
19. From the result, it is seen that maximum number of the employees (64.3%) are agree for induction programme helps to learn organization policies and procedures.

23.2.3 Training & Development

20. From the result, it is found that maximum number of employees (60.5%) of the employees are agree for induction programme gives confidence about work environment.
21. From the result, it is observed that most of the employees (76.8%) are agree for there is an adequate emphasis on developing managerial capabilities of the management staff through training.
22. From the result, it is seen that maximum number of the employees (39.5%) are agree for training in our organization includes social skills, general problem solving skills, broader knowledge of the organization and business.
23. From the result, it is seen that most of the employees (82.0%) are agree for to providing equal access to promotion, training and development by providing encouragement and assistance to those employees with family responsibilities.
24. From the result, it is indicated that maximum number of employees (56.9%) are agree for human relations competencies are adequately developed in this organization through training in human skills.

23.2.4 Performance Appraisal

25. Result shows that most of the employees (46.0%) are neither agree nor disagree for the performance appraisal at our organization undertakes to identify the developmental needs of its employees to help them attain their career goals.
26. From the result, it is found that maximum number of the employees (78.7%) are agree for the formal process of performance appraisals to provide feedback to employees to determine pay rises.
27. Result found that maximum numbers of the employees (78.7%) are agreeing for adequate growth opportunities are available in our organization for those who perform well.
28. Result indicate that most of the employees (82.0%) are agree for the appraisal system has scope for helping each employee discover his / her potential.

23.2.5 Compensation

29. It has been found that 45% employees are agree for the attract and retain employees primarily by paying a higher wage than our competitors.
30. Results found that maximum numbers of the employees (39.2%) are neither agree nor disagree for pay structure and scales of the Industry play a good supportive role in the life of employees.
31. Result found that maximum numbers of the employees (39.2%) are agree for the perks and allowances paid other than salary is very good.

23.2.6 Employee Relation

32. From the result, it is observed that maximum number of the employees (54.5%) are agree for the employees of the company gets their due respect and recognition from top management and board of directors.
33. From the result, it is indicated that maximum number of the employees (65.6%) are agree for the overall employer-employees or management employee relations are very good and cordial in the industry.
34. Result observed that most of the employees (60.5%) are agree for the role of management is supportive and employee friendly in the industry.

23.2.7 Reward, Award, & Incentives

35. Result shown that most of the employees (38.9%) are agreeing for the industry has a performance based incentives.
36. From the result, it can be seen that maximum number of the employees (68.3%) are agree for the industry has a competency based reward system.
37. From the result, it is seen that maximum number of the employees (63.7%) are agree for the fringe benefits provided by the company are good.
38. Result indicated that most of the employees (73.4%) are agree for the existing reward and incentive plans do not motivate us for better performance.

23.2.8 Promotion and Transfers

39. Result observed that most of the employees (87.4%) are agreeing for the promotion policy of the industry provides equal opportunities for career advancement.
40. From the result, it is observed that maximum number of the employees (72.9%) are agree for the promotion policy of the promotion policy helps the employees to raise their educational qualifications and motivation level.
41. From the result, it is found that most of the employees (48.2%) are agree for the promotion in the industry is unbiased and rational.
42. From the result, it is indicated that maximum number of the employees (73.2%) are agree for the promotion policy of the industry matches with the best in the industry.

23.2.9 HSE Policy

43. Result shown that maximum number (73.9%) of the employees are agree for the HSE policy of the industry actually ensures the safety of employees, plant and equipment.
44. Result observed that maximum numbers of the employees (61.8%) are agree for the medical facilities and regular check-ups are meeting your expectations.
45. Result found that most of the employees (55.2%) are agreeing for the industry provides personal accident insurance scheme.
46. Result shown that most of the employees (54.4%) are agree for the industry provides group medi-claim insurance scheme.
47. Result indicted that most of the employees (48.9%) are agree for the industry provides vacation childcare programmes.
48. Result shown that most of the employees (53.0%) are agreeing for the personal health care.
49. From the result, it is observed that maximum numbers of the employees (58.3%) are agreeing for the industry provides yearly master health check-up facility.

23.2.10 Welfare

50. From the result, it is indicated that most of the employees (48.2%) are agree for a number of recreational activities and occasional celebrations are organized in order to let employees show their creativity and enjoy.
51. Result observed that maximum number of the employees (57.5%) are agree for the organization pays for counseling services for employees experiencing, among other things, work/family stress.

52. From the result, it is seen that most of the employees (42.6%) are neutral about the continuous efforts are made in our organization to create a sense of belonging among employees and feel like a member of the corporate family.
53. Results shown that maximum numbers of the employees (51.3%) are agree for the organization provides subsidized food and transportation facility.
54. From the result, it is observed that maximum number (74.0%) of the employees are disagree for the organization provides loan facility and educational benefits to employees.

23.2.11 Work–Life Balance Policy

55. Result found that 38.5% of the employees are disagreeing for the industry provides programs to assist balancing demands of employees with working spouse.
56. It can be seen that 57.5% of the employees are agree for the Employees are encouraged to use work-life balance policies at this organization.
57. From the result, it is found that maximum number of the employees (63.8%) are disagree for the industry gives male and female employees the same level of access to 'work-life balance' policies.
58. From the result, it is seen that most of the employees (49.5%) are neither agree nor disagree for the industry provides all the relevant facilities and good work environment that helps to make the work-life balance.
59. From the result, it is indicated that maximum number of the employees (94.0%) are agree for the industry has overall a good strategic human resource practices.
60. Result observed that maximum numbers of the employees (62.0%) are agreeing for the HRM practices and policies have an impact on employees work-life balance.
61. Result found that maximum number of the employees (79.2%) are agree for that there is an effect of good human resource practices on employee's outcomes such as productivity.
62. Result shown that maximum numbers of the employees (79.2%) are agreeing for the HRM practices have an impact on employee job involvement.
63. Results found that maximum number of employees (64%) of the employees are agree for the HRM practices has an impact on employee job satisfaction.
64. Results found that maximum number of employees (72.8%) of the employees are agree for the HRM practices has an impact on employee job performance.

23.3 Findings based on Individual Related Variables

23.3.1 Work Centrality

65. It is evident from result that the distribution of scores on work centrality was found to be normal as skewness ($Sk=-0.66$) was found to be insignificant at 0.05 level of significance. The kurtosis ($Ku= -0.14$) was also found to be within limits at 0.05 level of significance.
66. Result evident that the distribution of scores on work centrality was found to be normal as skewness and kurtosis was found to be within limits at 0.05 level of significance.
67. It is evident from result that the distribution of scores on work centrality was found to be normal as skewness and kurtosis was found to be within limits at 0.05 level of significance.

23.3.2 Emotional Intelligence

68. It is evident from result that the distribution of scores on emotional intelligence was found to be normal as skewness ($Sk=-0.52$) was found to be insignificant at 0.05 level of significance. The kurtosis ($Ku=1.50$) was also found to be within limits at 0.05 level of significance.

23.4 Findings based on Family related Variables

69. It is also evident from result that the distribution of scores on family related variables was found to be normal as skewness and kurtosis was also found to be within limits at 0.05 level of significance.

23.5 Findings based on Work related Variables

23.5.1 Work load

70. Result evident that the distribution of scores on work load was found to be normal as skewness and kurtosis was also found to be within limits at 0.05 level of significance.

71. From the result, it is found that the distribution of scores on work load was found to be normal as skewness and kurtosis was also found to be within limits at 0.05 level of significance.

23.5.2 Work Flexibility

72. Result also evident that the distribution of scores on work flexibility was found to be normal as skewness and kurtosis was also found to be within limits at 0.05 level of significance.

23.6 Findings based on Work-Family Conflicts

73. It is evident from that score on work family conflict variables ranged between 1 and 5. The highest mean for work-family conflict related variables scores was found to be 4.1 and lowest mean of family related variables was found to be 3.5. The distribution of scores on work load was found to be normal as skewness and kurtosis was also found to be within limits at 0.05 level of significance.

23.7 Findings based on Job Satisfaction

74. From the result, it is observed that 84.8% employees are agreeing about the getting promotion as per qualification and experience. Whereas, 84% employees are agree about the favouritism does not have any role to play in their organization.

75. Result shown that 73.3% employees are satisfied with welfare facilities (medical etc.) provided by the Industry. Whereas, 49.5% employees are satisfied about the good prospects of advancement in their job.

76. Result indicated that 34.6% employees are satisfied with the general supervision in their department and 41% employees are satisfied about the working conditions in the industry. Whereas, 33.8% employees are satisfied about the payment they are getting in the industry.

77. Result also shown that 42.6% employees are satisfied about their supervisors takes into account their wishes and performance. While, 37.5% employees are satisfied about their job helped them to learn more skills.

78. Result found that 42.3% employees are satisfied their job security as long as they are doing good work in the industry.

23.8 One sample t-test for Job Satisfaction of Employees in Automobile Industry

79. Results found that, a job satisfaction variable ($p < 0.05$) is less than 5% level of significance. It can be concluded that there is a job satisfaction of employees among the Automobile Industry in Pune region.

24. Suggestions

Human resources are one of the most important assets in the organizations. Human resources provide an organization a source of sustainable competitive advantage in a highly competitive environment, facing a shortage of talents. Based on the study undertaken the following suggestions is being put forth for employees, management and the society. Work-life balance has always been a concern of those interested in the quality of working life and its relation to broader quality of life. Work life and personal life are the two sides of the same coin. Maintaining a reasonable balance between both is very important. The opinion of the employee regarding SHRM practices and its impact of work life balance is pointed out as follows:

1. Result shows that there is a lack of training of the employees on the areas such as social skills, general problem solving skills, broader knowledge of the organization and business. Therefore, researcher suggests that there is a need of proper training and developmental programs for the employees of automobile industry to improve social skills, general problem solving skills, broader knowledge of the organization and business.
2. As per the findings of performance appraisal, it is suggested that organizations should design performance appraisal system in such way that it should help employees to motivate and attain their career goals not threaten for them.
3. Researcher suggest that organization should provide lucrative and attractive pay structure and scales for the employees, also provides plentiful perks and allowances for a good supportive role in the life of employees of automobile industry.
4. Automobile industry should adopt a performance based incentives for encourage employees to perform better on their assigned task and duty.
5. Researcher suggested that employee promotion should be based on unbiased and rational.
6. From the research findings, researcher suggested that organizational should arrange a number of recreational activities and occasional celebrations are organized in order to let employees show their creativity and enjoy work-life balance in the industry.
7. ANOVA results shows that there is no impact of strategic human resource practices on employee job satisfaction. Hence, researcher suggested that human resource manager should create innovative practices for achieving higher level of job satisfaction among employees of automobile industry.
8. Hypothesis results shows that organization should develop proper human resource practices for proper work load and other work related variables for getting higher level of work-life balance approach among the employees of automobile industry in Pune region.

25. Suggestions for Future Research

While conducting the present study certain aspects could not be dealt with, due to constraints of time and cost. Also, through this research work areas can be identified for further research. The present study has been undertaken to know the impact of HR Planning, recruitment, selection & induction, training & development, performance appraisal, Compensation, employee relation, reward, awards & incentives, promotion & transfers, SHE policy (safety, health and environment), and welfare on work life balance of selected Automobile Industry in Pune region.

Automobile Industry has to make their strategies for employee's development and increase the strength & improve the positive attitude in employees themselves. For improving the human resource management practices in Industry, the following suggestions are made for future research:

- The link between the SHRM practices & Work-life balance.
- The present study was conducted on 400 employees but in future study may be a larger sample.
- The socio economic and changes in the standard of living of employees.
- The job satisfaction of employees in Automobile Industry in Pune region.
- The implications of proposed suggestions to improve the satisfaction of workers.
- The present study evaluates the impact of HR practices on Job Satisfaction and Commitment levels for managerial employees in the Automobile Industry.
- Compensation strategies and its comparative analysis may be performed for various Industries in region.
- HR practices can be further, independently studied in the global context to understand their individual impact on employee's Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment.
- This topic may further be studied through a different angle of managing diversity in organization and the changing HR practices.
- Further studies can be done on understanding work life balance in different sectors such manufacturing, BPO, financial services.
- An attempt may be made to understand the effect of work life balance practices adopted in organisations to improve employees work life balance.

26. Conclusions

The present study has been undertaken to know the impact of HR Planning, recruitment, selection & induction, training & development, performance appraisal, Compensation, employee relation, reward, awards & incentives, promotion & transfers, SHE policy (Safety, Health and Environment), and welfare of selected Automobile Industry in Pune region. The nature of Automobile Industry such as National and Multinational under private industry in Pune city, Ranjangaon, Sanaswadi, Chakan and Pimpri-Chinchwad area have been considered for the study. The unit of statistical population is the representative of the concerned Automobile Industry and data are collected from them by scientific methods.

The Automobile Industry selected for this study has adopted suitable policies and regulations so that work-life balance is higher for these organizations. However the organizations should know to identify the benefits of work-life balance the employees so that it can achieve its business objective and can gain competitive advantage over their competitors.

The study utilized a survey method and the results of 400 respondents were the basis for statistical findings. The information obtained through this study will help the employees to address their needs, so that they can implement their requirements and can retain their best talents.

The Automobile Industries selected for this study have adopted suitable human resource management practices and policies on work life balance. As employees are the bases for Industry, retention of employees is a major focus for HR department.

Thus it can be concluded by indicating that organizations should concentrate in identifying employees and also identify their needs with respect to their career, education and family. So that this positive approach of the organization will improve the balancing the work and life of employees.

The results of this research indicate that a large proportion of people lack awareness of work-life balance issues and the laws governing them. The respondents' answers show that both the state and employers are in a position to enhance work-life balance by providing benefits and proper information in this regard.

There was a time when the boundaries between work and home were fairly clear. Today, however, work is likely to invade personal life and maintaining work-life balance is no simple task. Still, work-life balance isn't out of reach. Start by evaluating your relationship to work. Then apply specific HR strategies as mentioned above to help you strike a healthier balance.

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